

Chemical Constituents of *Eupatorium chinense* L.

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EUPATORIUM L. (Compositae) represents a large genus of herbs, shrubs and undershrubs with varied biological properties¹. *Eupatorium chinense* L. is one of the few species found in countries like China and India. The paper presents a report of analysis of a species of Indian origin identified as *E. chinense* L. (compositae) which appears to be different from that of *E. chinense* varieties reported earlier². The plant has shown mild diuretic property in the preliminary screening.

Experimental

The air-dried aerial parts (700 g) were extracted with Et₂O-MeOH-petrol (1 : 1 : 1) and the resulting extract (14.6 g) was dissolved in MeOH and chilled by keeping in a refrigerator overnight. The solids fraction-I (fatty materials separated) was filtered out (~3.4 g) and the soluble fraction-II obtained was concentrated to get an extract (~11.2 g). Fraction-I was separated by column chromatography (silica gel 60; Merck) using petroleum ether (PE), PE/Et₂O (95 : 5, 90 : 10, 85 : 15, 80 : 20, 75 : 25, 50 : 50, 25 : 75), Et₂O, Et₂O/MeOH (90 : 10 and 80 : 20) to get 11 fractions (100 ml each) which were monitored by tlc (silica gel, 20 cm × 20 cm plates × 1.5 mm thickness) using appropriate solvent systems, PE/Et₂O, 9 : 1 (A), 4 : 1 (B), 3 : 2 (C), 1 : 1 (D), 2 : 3 (E), C₆H₆/Me₂CO, 9 : 1 (F) and 8 : 2 (G).

The compounds isolated by preparative tlc were identified from their ir (Perkin-Elmer 299B), mass (VG Analytical Organic Mass spectrometer, 70 eV) and ¹H nmr (Bruker WM 400) spectra in comparison with the reported ones³.

Results and Discussion

¹H nmr spectra of first column chromatographic fractions 1–3 showed only signals due to long-chain hydrocarbons. Fractions 4–5 afforded a white solid (~1.0 g), tlc of the fractions (solvent system B) afforded one minor spot 1 (*R*_f 0.92) and another intense spot 2 (*R*_f 0.89).¹ The former was identified as squalene and the latter as taraxasterol palmitate.

Squalene: Compound 1 was identified as squalene, δ 1.35, 1.75, 2.10, 5.11 and *m/z* (rel. int.) 81 (100), 137 (38), 95 (25), 93 (20), 70 (19), 121 (16), 136 (13), 410, [*M*]⁺ calcd. for C₃₀H₅₀ (11).

Taraxasterol palmitate: Compound 2, colourless needles, m.p. 102°; [*α*]_D²⁰ +71 (c 0.356); *ν*_{max} (KBr) 1722 (CO), 1633 (C=C) and 863 (=CH₂); δ 0.76, 0.86, 0.93, 0.97, 1.03, 1.25, 2.29, 4.45, 4.62; *m/z* (rel. int.) 664, [*M*]⁺ calcd. for C₄₆H₈₀O₂ (68), 408 (29), 189 (100), 57 (62), 55 (54), 109 (55) suggested it to be taraxasterol palmitate. The findings agreed with reported values⁴.

Hydrolysis of compound 2 yielded colourless needles, m.p. 226°, which gave ¹H nmr signals characteristic of taraxasterol. The side-chain acid obtained on methylation and mass spectral analysis was found to be palmitic acid.

Fraction 6–8 afforded a major compound 3 (*R*_f 0.76 in solvent system C) which gave green fluorescence in uv light. The compound was identified as methyl ripariochromene A.

Methyl ripariochromene A: Compound 3, colourless needles. δ 1.49, 1.56, 2.59, 3.88, 3.97, 5.61, 6.30, 7.25; *m/z* (rel. int.) 203 (7), 247 (100) and 262 [*M*]⁺ calcd. for C₁₅H₁₈O₄ (16) suggested its identity as methyl ripariochromene A⁵.

Fractions 9 and 10 also showed a spot corresponding to compound 3 and two additional faint spots (*R*_f 0.64 and 0.55) which have not been identified.

The methanol soluble fraction-I was found to consist almost exclusively of methyl ripariochromene A (3).

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References

- 1 R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAVAR and L. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956 p 113.
- 2 T. TAKEMI, M. TATSUSHI, U. AKIKO, N. ISAMI and Y. OSAMU, *Jpn. Kokai Tokkyo Koho*, 1980, **80**, 45, 632, Y. DEQUAN, and K. HUAIPING, *Zhongcaoyao*, 1983, **14**, 100, K. ITO, Y. SAKAKIBARA and M. HARUNA, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, **21**, 715.
- 3 J. G. GRASSELLI and W. M. RITCHEY, "CRC Atlas of Spectral Data and Physical Constants for Organic Compounds", CRC Press, Cleveland, 1975, Vols I-VI.
- 4 M. YOSHIZAKI, H. SUZUKI, K. SANO, K. KIMURA and T. NAMBA, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1974, **99**, 338, B. TALAPATRA, R. MUKHOPADHYAY and S. K. TALAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 296.
- 5 D. K. TAYLOR and J. A. WRIGHT, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, **10**, 1665.